

KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND ATTITUDE ON CLIENT SAFETY DURING CLINICAL DUTY OF BSN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204627>

ABSTRACT

This study emphasizes how critical nursing education is to producing skilled healthcare workers who are dedicated to patient safety. Focusing on the transition phase for Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students, the study highlights obstacles such as connecting academic knowledge with practical application, limited hands-on experience, and exposure to various clinical scenarios. Conducted in Quezon City, Philippines, the research evaluates how Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes correspond with patient safety criteria, in line with national educational benchmarks. Through a descriptive correlational research approach including 200 Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students, the study investigates interactions within healthcare settings, attempting to uncover difficulties and solutions. The study explores the professional development of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students, emphasizing the integration of theoretical and practical knowledge as critical to building competence in patient safety. According to findings, BSN students show substantial knowledge (4.28/5) and skills (4.45/5) in ensuring client safety, demonstrating proficiency in patient safety tasks. Their attitudes toward patient safety are also positive, aligning with research that shows a strong link between perceived competence and safer practices. However, common issues affecting patient rights were identified, with frequent compromises on the "Right Time," "Right Dose," "Right Medication," "Right Patient Education," and "Right Patient." This highlights systemic challenges, such as scheduling issues or information gaps, which may affect patient safety and care quality.

Keywords: *Client safety, clinical duty, knowledge, skills, attitude, BSN students*

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of nursing education is essential for nurturing skilled healthcare professionals who can guarantee patient safety. One important element of nursing education is ensuring an ideal connection between theoretical understanding and its practical application in real clinical environments. For Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students, this phase marks a crucial shift from theoretical classroom learning to hands-on clinical responsibilities. It is necessary to ensure that these students not only acquire the necessary knowledge about client safety but also demonstrate suitable attitude while fulfilling the clinical duties of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City, as this is fundamental for the well-being of patients (Smith et al., 2018).

In nursing practice, patient safety is a core principle. Patient safety is now a top priority for global health, according to the World Health Organization (WHO) (WHO, 2019). Assessing practice readiness has always been challenging as nursing student preparedness has become a growing concern throughout the years for educational programs (Shahsavari et al., 2020). A key stage in a nurse's career is the transition from nursing education to professional practice. Students bridge the gap between theory and practice during the clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. Learning how to provide safe care, interact with the healthcare team successfully, and adjust to changing clinical situations are all part of this transformation (Hensel et al., 2017).

Several research studies have emphasized the difficulties nursing students encounter in connecting theoretical knowledge with practical application in real clinical situations. Problems like inadequate hands-on experience, limited exposure to diverse clinical cases, and insufficient supervision can impede students' capacity to effectively utilize their knowledge. Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the elements that might impact or not the correlation between knowledge, skills, and attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City. This understanding is important for improving their performance in clinical settings and, consequently, guaranteeing the safety of patients.

In the distinctive setting of Quezon City, it is highly important to investigate how Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students' knowledge aligns with their knowledge, skills, and attitude. The encounters these students have, their interactions with patients, peers, and the healthcare surroundings, offer valuable understanding into the obstacles they encounter and the approaches they use to guarantee patient safety. Exploring these dynamics within the specific context of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City allows for a targeted and context-specific examination, providing detailed viewpoints on the challenges being addressed.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) of the Philippines (CHED Memorandum Order No. 15, s. 2017) establishes standards for nursing programs. According to these regulations, nursing students must demonstrate competency in patient care, which includes protecting client safety, to graduate. By the end of the first year, students will

showcase basic nursing skills in simulated scenarios, ensuring safe and suitable care using the nursing process. Moving to the second year, they'll extend this to caring for mothers, newborns, children, families, and communities, focusing on safety and holistic care. In the third year, students will deal with more complex health issues, applying the nursing process while integrating research and evidence-based practice. Finally, in the fourth year, they'll demonstrate advanced skills, catering to diverse client groups and readying themselves for entry-level nursing positions. These requirements are aligned with the evaluation of students' client safety knowledge, skills, and attitude.

According to research, well-prepared nursing students are more likely to deliver high-quality care, which in turn improves patient outcomes. On the other hand, underprepared students could be part of mistakes and unfavorable outcomes (Kennedy, Regehr, & Baker, 2009). Therefore, evaluating the knowledge, skills, and attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City in ensuring client safety may have an impact on patient outcomes in the healthcare facilities where they study.

This research is in line with the wider global healthcare objectives, underscoring the significance of patient safety and the essential role played by nursing professionals. Studies addressing the connection between knowledge, skills, and attitude in nursing students have implications not only for nursing education but also for shaping healthcare policies and practices (Chen et al., 2017). By pinpointing the challenges confronted by Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City and comprehending how these challenges impact their actions, this study contributes to evidence-based interventions capable of bridging the gap between theory and practice.

Moreover, this investigation explores the educational approaches and support systems within Quezon City. Examining the effectiveness of teaching methods, clinical oversight, and feedback mechanisms offers valuable insights into the institutional factors influencing the relationship between knowledge, skills, and attitude. Understanding these elements can guide the development of institutional policies, faculty training programs, and curriculum enhancements tailored to the specific requirements of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in Quezon City.

Research Questions

Nursing education is fundamental in shaping skilled healthcare providers, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge practically is crucial for patient safety. The transition from classroom studies to clinical duties is a vital stage for Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. The problem lies in the need to comprehensively investigate and analyze the relationships between the theoretical knowledge acquired, the practical skills applied, and the attitudes embraced by these students in the specific context of client safety during clinical duty. This study intends to answer the following questions:

1. What is the capability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty in terms of:
 - 1.1. Knowledge

- 1.2. Skills
- 1.3. Attitude
2. How is client safety affected during clinical duty in terms of 10 rights in medication by Kozier & Erb's Fundamentals of Nursing:
 - 2.1. Right patient
 - 2.2. Right medication
 - 2.3. Right dose
 - 2.4. Right route
 - 2.5. Right time
 - 2.6. Right patient education
 - 2.7. Right documentation
 - 2.8. Right to refuse
 - 2.9. Right assessment
 - 2.10. Right evaluation
3. What is the correlation between knowledge, skills, and attitude among Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty?
4. What challenges do Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students typically face during their clinical duty such as:
 - 4.1. Hands-on experience
 - 4.2. Patient-to-student ratio
 - 4.3. Adequate supervision
 - 4.4. Communication within healthcare teams
5. Based on the findings of the study, what measures can be proposed to enhance client safety in clinical duty?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researchers utilized a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. Using this method, the researchers described the importance of client safety during clinical duty. The descriptive method was used to identify the proficiency and level of knowledge, skills, and attitude of the respondents about client safety during clinical duty. To find the relationship among knowledge, skills, and attitude, the correlational method was used.

The study, which concentrated on the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), was conducted on the premises of Quezon City. This included the academic and clinical environments that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students worked in, such as classrooms, simulation labs, and clinical settings. The administration of the survey and the gathering of data took place in locations that were comfortable. The study also took into account the privacy and ethical issues surrounding research conducted in educational institutions.

The researchers employed a convenience sampling. The study's population consisted of 200 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program in 14 schools of Quezon City. These students were studying foundational nursing courses in the hospital's clinical setting, as well as in their skills lab and classroom. The study tool was a survey that assessed the relationship among knowledge, skills, and attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students concerning client safety during clinical duty.

The primary tool utilized in this study was a survey designed to explore the enhancement passage between Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students and their adherence to client safety protocols during clinical duty. The researcher gave validity to their question. Taking a validator who has been in the medical field that enhances the validity of the questionnaire. All of them approved it, which led the researcher to use it.

To get the appropriate data needed, the researcher had questionnaires with 5 parts. Part 1 was the tool used to determine the level of knowledge on client safety during clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. Part 2 was the tool used to determine the level of skills in client safety during clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. Part 3 was the tool that was used to get the level of attitude on client safety during clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. Part 4 was the tool used to identify how the client's safety is affected during clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. Part 5 was the tool used to identify the challenges to client safety during clinical duty of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students. This survey or questionnaire was designed to gather data, assess knowledge, and evaluate client safety, providing valuable insights for nursing education and improving student understanding.

The researcher collaborated with nursing educators and experts to confirm the relevance and appropriateness of the content. A pilot test was also conducted with a small sample of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students to identify any confusing language in the questions. The researchers also conducted a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha to ensure the questionnaires were reliable. The results demonstrated that the knowledge section had an excellent reliability score of 0.953. The skills section got 0.865 and attitude section got 0.859 which indicates a high reliability score.

RESULTS

1. Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding Client Safety

Table 1.1: Summary of Assessment on the Capability of BSN Students

Variables	Average	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Knowledge	4.28	Moderately knowledgeable	3
Skills	4.45	Moderately skillful	2
Attitude	4.55	Moderately acceptable	1

Table 1.1 illustrates the knowledge, skills, and attitude (KSA) of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty. For knowledge, the average score of 4.28 indicates a moderately knowledgeable level. The results show a higher average score (4.45) for skills compared to knowledge, indicating that BSN students are moderately skillful in applying their knowledge to patient care. The highest average score (4.55) was for attitude, signifying a moderately acceptable attitude towards client safety.

1.2. Knowledge of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding Client Safety

Table 1.2: Knowledge

Items	Average	Verbal Description	Rank
Familiarity with the key principles of patient safety.	4.46	Moderately knowledgeable	1
Understands the potential risks and complications associated with common nursing procedures.	4.34	Moderately knowledgeable	2
Prioritizing patient safety concerns and escalate them properly	4.32	Moderately knowledgeable	3
Knowledgeable about infection control guidelines and practice	4.31	Moderately knowledgeable	4

Awareness of legal and ethical considerations related to client safety.	4.29	Moderately knowledgeable	5
Understanding the guidelines and protocols for ensuring patient safety in my assigned clinical area.	4.29	Moderately knowledgeable	5
Identifying potential safety hazards in the clinical environment.	4.25	Moderately knowledgeable	6
Familiarization with the common types of medical errors and their consequences.	4.19	Moderately knowledgeable	7
Reporting and responding to safety incidents.	4.19	Moderately knowledgeable	8
Performing essential clinical skills while maintaining patient safety.	4.17	Moderately knowledgeable	9
Total	4.28	Moderately Knowledgeable	N=200

Note. 4.81-5.00 very knowledgeable, 3.41-4.80 moderately knowledgeable, 2.61-3.40 somewhat knowledgeable, 1.81-2.60 less knowledgeable, 1.00-1.80 not knowledgeable

Table 1.2 illustrates the capability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty in terms of Knowledge. Showing an average of 4.46 and 4.29, the respondents are moderately knowledgeable for familiarity with the key principles or aware of legal and ethical considerations related to client safety. With an average of 4.34 and 4.25, the respondents are moderately knowledgeable that they understand the potential risks, safety hazards, and complications associated with common nursing procedures. With an average of 4.31, respondents are moderately knowledgeable about infection control guidelines and practices for ensuring patient safety in my assigned clinical area. With an average of 4.19, respondents are moderately knowledgeable in familiarity with the common types of medical errors and their consequences. Lastly, with an average of 4.17, the respondents are moderately knowledgeable that they can correctly perform essential clinical skills while maintaining patient safety. As a result, with an average of 4.28, the respondents are moderately knowledgeable that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) student has knowledge regarding Client Safety.

1.3. Skills of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding Client Safety

Table 1.3: Skills

Items	Average	Verbal Description	Rank
Maintaining a clean and sterile environment.	5.00	Very skillful	1
Assessing client risks for falls.	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Implementing fall prevention strategies.	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Communicating effectively with clients and other healthcare providers about safety concerns.	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Performing hand hygiene according to recommended protocols	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Using personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately.	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Taking vital signs accurately and efficiently.	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Performing basic assessments (e.g., pain, neurological, respiratory).	4.50	Moderately skillful	2
Performing medication administration safely and accurately.	4.00	Moderately skillful	3
Identifying and responding to adverse medication reactions.	4.00	Moderately skillful	3
Total	4.45	Moderately Skillful	N=200

Note. 4.81-5.00 very skillful, 3.41-4.80 moderately skillful, 2.61-3.40 somewhat skillful, 1.81-2.60 less skillful, 1.00-1.80 not skillful

Table 1.3 illustrates the capability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty in terms of Skills. Showing an average of 5.00, the respondents are very skillful in maintaining a clean and sterile environment. With an average of 4.50, the respondents are moderately skillful in assessing client risks for falls, implementing fall prevention strategies, communicating

effectively with clients and other healthcare providers about safety concerns, performing hand hygiene according to recommended protocols, using personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately, taking vital signs accurately and efficiently, and perform basic assessments (e.g., pain, neurological, respiratory). Lastly, with an average of 4.00, the respondents are moderately skillful in performing medication administration safely and accurately and identifying and responding to adverse medication reactions. As a result, with an average of 4.45, the respondents are moderately skillful that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) student has skills regarding Client Safety.

1.4. Attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding Client Safety.

Table 1.4: Attitude

Items	Average	Verbal Description	Rank
Believe that client safety is their top priority when providing care.	4.74	Moderately acceptable	1
Open to feedback and willing to improve their safety practices.	4.74	Moderately acceptable	1
Open to learning new things about client safety.	4.73	Moderately acceptable	2
I believe that it is important to work as a team to ensure client safety.	4.73	Moderately acceptable	2
Willing to ask for help when unsure about a safe practice.	4.72	Moderately acceptable	3
Committed to continuous improvement in their nursing practice.	4.68	Moderately acceptable	4
Approaches clinical duties with a positive attitude.	4.60	Moderately acceptable	5
Confident in their ability to provide safe and competent care to patients.	4.45	Moderately acceptable	6
Comfortable in speaking up if they see something that could harm a client.	4.38	Moderately acceptable	7

Willing to ask for help when they are unsure about how to perform a procedure safely.	3.69	Moderately acceptable	8
Total	4.55	Moderately Acceptable	N=200

Note. 4.81-5.00 highly acceptable, 3.41-4.80 moderately acceptable, 2.61-3.40 somewhat acceptable, 1.81-2.60 less acceptable, 1.00-1.80 not acceptable

Table 1.4 illustrates the capability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty in terms of Attitude. Showing an average of 4.74, the respondents are moderately acceptable that the client safety is my top priority when providing care and that it is important to work as a team to ensure client safety. With an average of 4.73, the respondents are moderately acceptable in that they are open to learn new things about client safety and it is important to work as a team to ensure client safety. With an average of 4.72, the respondents are moderately acceptable that they are willing to ask for help when unsure about a safe practice. With an average of 4.68, the respondents are moderately acceptable that they are committed to continuous improvement in nursing practice. With an average of 4.60, the respondents are moderately acceptable to approach clinical duties with a positive attitude. With an average of 4.45, the respondents are moderately acceptable that they are confident in their ability to provide safe and competent care to patients. With an average of 4.38, the respondents are moderately acceptable that they are comfortable speaking up if they see something that could harm a client. Lastly, with an average of 3.69, the respondents are moderately acceptable that they are willing to ask for help when they are unsure about how to perform a procedure safely. As a result, with an average of 4.55, the respondents are moderately acceptable that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) student has an attitude regarding Client Safety.

2. Rights that affect client safety during clinical duty

Table 2: Rights

Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rate
Right Time	144	72%	1
Right Medication	127	63.5%	2
Right Dose	125	62.5%	3
Right Patient	125	62.5%	3
Right Patient Education	123	61.5%	4
Right Assessment	118	59%	5
Right Route	116	58%	6
Right Documentation	111	55.5%	7

Right Evaluation	104	52%	8
Right To Refuse	93	46.5%	9
Multiple Response			N=200

Note. 10 rights of Medication by Kozier & Erb's Fundamentals of Nursing

Table 2 illustrates how client safety is affected by being frequently compromised during clinical duty in terms of 10 rights of patients. Showing a frequency of 144, the respondents choose "Right Time" to be the most compromised. With a frequency of 127, the respondents choose "Right Medication" to be second most compromised. With the frequency of 125, the respondents choose "Right Dose" and "Right Patient" as the third most compromised. With a frequency of 123, the respondents choose "Right Patient Education" to be fourth most compromised. With a frequency of 118, the respondents choose "Right Patient" to be fifth most compromised. With a frequency of 116, the respondents choose "Right Route" to be sixth most compromised. With a frequency of 111, the respondents choose "Right Documentation" to be seventh most compromised. With a frequency of 104, the respondents choose "Right Evaluation" to be the second to the least compromised. With a frequency of 93, the respondents choose "Right To Refuse" to be least most compromised.

3. Correlation among knowledge skills, and attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding Client Safety during Clinical Duty

Table 3.1: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Patient

Table 3.1: Right Patient

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	7.880	.096	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	7.684	.104	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	7.152	.067	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.1, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.2: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Medication

Table 3.2: Right Medication

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	3.001	.558	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	3.221	.522	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	2.417	.491	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.2, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.3: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Dose

Table 3.3: Right Dose

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	3.227	.521	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	2.802	.592	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	3.870	.276	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.3, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.4: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Route

Table 3.4: Right Route

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	1.898	.755	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	.821	.936	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	2.535	.469	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.4, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.5: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Time

Table 3.5: Right Time

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	6.721	.151	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	1.537	.820	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	3.781	.286	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.5, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.6: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Patient Education

Table 3.6: Right Patient Education

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	6.626	.157	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	5.824	.213	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	.146	.986	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.6, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.7: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Documentation

Table 3.7: Right Documentation

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	6.788	.148	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	4.704	.319	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	4.999	.172	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.7, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.8: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right to Refuse

Table 3.8: Right to Refuse

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	2.625	.622	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	4.385	.356	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	2.983	.394	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.8, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.9: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Assessment

Table 3.9: Right Assessment

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	8.486	.075	Accepted	Not Significant
Skills	2.442	.655	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	4.910	.179	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

Based on the results in Table 3.9, it appears that there is no significant relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and Right Patient, as all p-values are above the typical threshold of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 3.10: Results of hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between KSA and Right Evaluation

Table 3.10: Right Evaluation

Competency	x ² -Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	10.403	.034	Rejected	Significant
Skills	2.607	.626	Accepted	Not Significant
Attitude	1.169	.760	Accepted	Not Significant

Note. >0.05 - accepted/not significant, <0.05 - rejected/significant

In Table 3.10, the results indicate a mixed outcome regarding the relationship between KSA (Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude) and the ability to perform the right evaluation. For knowledge, the chi-square value is 10.403 with a p-value of 0.034, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, suggesting a significant relationship between knowledge and the ability to perform the right evaluation. For skills and attitude, however, the p-values are 0.626 and 0.760 respectively, indicating that there is no significant relationship between these competencies and the ability to perform the right evaluation.

4. Challenges that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students typically face during their Clinical Duty

Table 4: Challenges

Choices	Frequency	Rate
Hands-on experience	93	1
Communication within healthcare teams	51	2
Patient-to-student ratio	37	3
Adequate Supervision	19	4
Total		N=200

Table 4 illustrates the challenges that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students typically face during their clinical duty. Hands-on Experience, with a frequency score of 93, this option was the most commonly chosen by the respondents. Communication within Healthcare Teams, with a frequency of 51 and a rate of 2, shows that although it was chosen less frequently, respondents still thought it was essential. Patient-to-Student Ratio, this option was chosen less frequently, with a frequency of 37 and a rate of 3. Adequate Supervision, with a rate of 4 and the lowest frequency of

19, this option was chosen the least and is thought to be the least significant of the options offered.

DISCUSSION

Based on the study of Eraut (2004, 2012); Lave (2009), and Tynjälä et al.(2014) professional knowledge includes social-cultural understanding, reflecting recommended conditions and processes in the current environment, and self-regulatory skills. Integrating theoretical and practical knowledge is crucial for professional development. The average knowledge of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty, as indicated in Table 1.1 is 4.28. This falls within the range of agreement (3.41-4.80), indicating a significant level of understanding and competence in ensuring client safety.

On the other hand, the average skills of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in ensuring client safety during clinical duty, as presented in Table 1.2, is 4.45. This falls within the range of confidence (3.41-4.80), demonstrating a solid level of proficiency and capability in executing tasks related to client safety, In accordance with the research conducted by Smith et al. (2018) students with a strong dedication to patient safety were to be more inclined to participate in safe nursing procedures.

The average attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students regarding client safety during clinical duty, as indicated in Table 1.3 is 4.55. This also falls within the range of agreement (3.41-4.80), indicating a generally positive outlook towards prioritizing and ensuring client safety, correlating it with the study of Gardner et al. (2016), which identified that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students who perceived their competence in patient safety are inclined towards safer nursing practices.

As explained by the study of Tabassum et al. (2016) patient rights is a key concern for healthcare professionals and policymakers globally. It serves as an essential benchmark for healthcare quality and underpins clinical care standards. In another study by Yaghobian et al. (2014) patient rights serve as a fundamental basis for establishing standards in therapeutic services. With increasing attention to human rights by international organizations, the concept of patient rights has gained prominence, significantly influencing healthcare settings worldwide. According to Table 2, the 5 most affected rights during clinical duty are the following. The most common is the Right Time which has a frequency of 144 (72%) of replies, this suggests that there is often a compromise in the timing of drug administration, potentially as a result of variables including hectic schedules, delayed prescription delivery, or scheduling problems. Right dose is compromised with 125 (62.5%) of replies, this denotes circumstances in which prescriptions are given at the wrong doses, perhaps resulting in negative side effects or insufficient care. Right Medication has a frequency of 127 (63.5%) of responses, this right's compromises allude to situations in which the incorrect medication may be given, whether as a result of incorrect labeling, confusion

with similar-looking pharmaceuticals, or other circumstances. Next is the Right Patient Education which has a frequency of 123 (61.5%) of the responses, this indicates that patients may not have received all the necessary information about their prescriptions, such as dosage guidelines, possible adverse effects, and precautions. Lastly is the Right Patient which has a frequency of 125 (62.5%) of the responses, this illustrates situations in which the wrong patient receives medication, which can have adverse effects on both the patient and the healthcare professional.

As elaborated in the study of Hamid Safarpour et al. (2017), integrating theoretical foundations with educational experiences is essential for developing knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enhance patient safety effectively. The findings presented in Table 3.1 to 3.10, employing Chi-square, it is evident that there's no significant correlation among the knowledge, skills, and attitude of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students concerning client safety during clinical duty. This observation suggests that the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of BSN students are not significantly interconnected within the nursing domain, implying that improvements in knowledge and skills do not necessarily lead to changes in attitudes toward prioritizing client safety, highlighting a potential gap in the comprehensive approach to nursing education and practice.

The findings from Table 4 underscore the challenges encountered by Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students during their clinical duties, particularly in relation to hands-on experience, with a frequency of 93. These challenges have a notable impact on the student's learning and growth within their educational journey. This emphasizes the significance of addressing barriers to hands-on learning opportunities in nursing education to facilitate the comprehensive development of future nurses, since insufficient hands-on experience may diminish nursing students' confidence in delivering safe patient care. Connecting it to the study conducted by Jamshidi et al. (2016), students with lower levels of confidence are at a higher risk of making errors. Therefore, it is crucial for nursing educators to prioritize providing students with opportunities to practice clinical skills in a controlled environment before they begin their clinical rotations.

After considering the study's results in relation to Patricia Benner's well-known "From Novice to Expert" framework, it is clear that Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students' path to becoming competent professionals entails a complex development of knowledge, skills, and attitude, which is consistent with Benner's stages of nursing proficiency.

The development from novice where people are task-oriented and strongly dependent on rules to expert where practice is guided by intuition and holistic understanding is highlighted by Benner's framework. According to this study, Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students demonstrate a strong comprehension and competency in maintaining client safety, which is consistent with Benner's model and indicates a degree of proficiency that is within the range of agreement.

The study also emphasizes how knowledge, skills, and attitude are all interrelated when it comes to client safety. Benner's emphasis on the integration of theoretical underpinnings with practical experiences to enable full professional growth is echoed in this holistic approach to nursing education.

This study implies that nursing education should emphasize developing the proper attitude and mindset toward patient safety in addition to providing knowledge and technical skills, in light of Benner's framework. It highlights how important it is for students to have organized learning opportunities that help them close the knowledge gap between theory and practice and advance from being beginners to skilled practitioners.

This research provides valuable understanding and data about the professional growth of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students and emphasizes how critical it is that nursing education adheres to the ideas presented in Benner's "From Novice to Expert" framework. Nursing programs can better prepare students for the complex realities of clinical practice and assure the delivery of safe and effective patient care by addressing the problems that have been highlighted and supporting a comprehensive approach to teaching.

Conclusions

To sum up, this study examined BSN students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA) about patient safety during clinical rotations. Although the study's respondents had a strong base of skills and knowledge, no apparent connection between these elements was established. The right time, right drug, right dose, right patient education, and right patient as commonly affected were among the topics highlighted by the analysis of patient rights. Among the difficulties noted was a lack of practical experience. It will be important going ahead to put policies into place that will improve possibilities for practical training and strengthen knowledge of patient safety procedures in order to guarantee safer clinical settings.

Recommendations

College. The researchers recommends that college needs to think about putting in place focused interventions meant to enhance students' comprehension and application of safety procedures during clinical practice in order to improve client safety results. This can entail adding interactive workshops with a particular focus on client safety principles, case studies, and practical simulation exercises.

Nursing instructors. The researchers suggests that nursing instructors should place a strong emphasis on helping students develop their critical thinking and decision-making skills, especially in circumstances where patient safety could be at risk. Giving students the chance to participate in debriefing sessions and reflective practice after clinical experiences might help them get a deeper comprehension of the challenges associated with maintaining patient safety.

In order to improve students' comprehension of patient safety within the larger healthcare system, the College should also look for chances for multidisciplinary engagement with other healthcare professionals. This could entail cooperative projects, joint training sessions, and shared learning opportunities that support a safety culture among various healthcare specialties.

Curriculum. In the future, the curriculum should be continuously assessed and evaluated to make sure it continues to be relevant to the changing demands of the healthcare sector and is in line with patient safety best practices. It is recommended that nursing educators are motivated to conduct additional research in this field. The study's conclusions can be utilized to guide upcoming endeavors that strive to enhance client safety results and progress nursing education overall.

Future researchers. The researchers recommend that future researchers must prioritize addressing the concerning negative findings regarding the learning gaps among Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students in upholding patient safety, particularly in relation to the timing of medication administration. The lack of correlation between the students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes highlights the need to investigate the underlying reasons affecting adherence to the 10 rights of medication administration. Formulating interventions or educational approaches to address these gaps is essential to lessening such incidents and sustaining patient safety practices within nursing student associates.

Moreover, it is crucial to confront the obstacles highlighted by students regarding the insufficiency of hands-on experience. This entails a thorough examination of the factors that contribute to this gap and devising strategies to offer students increased opportunities for practical learning within clinical environments. Such attempts hold significant potential to enrich students' overall learning journey and nurture their professional growth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations are necessary for research projects as all respondents had moral and legal rights. For this study, the researcher ensured that they did not invade their privacy without their consent, that the research did not hurt their feelings, and that all information received from them was acknowledged and accurately represented. Some ethical considerations this study ensured for the respondents were:

1. Research respondents participated voluntarily, free from any coercion or undue influence, and their rights, dignity, and autonomy were respected and appropriately protected.
2. Researchers and respondents were given appropriate information about the purpose, methods, and intended uses of the research, and what their participation in the research entailed.
3. Research respondent preferences regarding anonymity were respected and

participant requirements concerning the confidential nature of information and personal data were respected.

Beneficence is the principle of doing good and preventing harm. In the context of this study, the researcher maximized the potential benefits of the study and minimized the potential risks to respondents. The researcher also made sure that the benefits of the study exceed the risks.

Autonomy, on the other hand, is the principle of self-governance and the ability to make independent decisions. In the context of this study, the researchers granted the respondents the right to self-determination and make informed decisions.

Acknowledgments

The completion of this research project has been made possible through the generous support and contributions of numerous individuals and organizations, whom the researchers would like to acknowledge with heartfelt gratitude.

The researchers would like to thank God for his mercy and supernatural guidance during this research journey. His blessings have helped them overcome obstacles and illuminate the way to understanding by giving them courage, insight, and inspiration.

The researchers' deepest appreciation goes out to their adviser, Professor Alexander Palaganas, RN, who has provided constant support, direction, and valuable insights during our study project. His guidance has been crucial in determining the focus and approach of this research.

The researchers would especially want to thank their Research Professor, Professor Kevin De Vera MAN, RN, LPT, whose knowledge and suggestions have substantially improved the level and scope of our study. His support and insightful critique have been extremely helpful in refining the concepts in this work.

The researchers extend their deepest gratitude to the validators, Prof. Michael John Agustin, RN, MAN, Prof. Alvin V. Arroyo, RN, MSN, and Prof. Romeo R. Contreras, RN, MAN, who meticulously reviewed and validated their research instrument. Their expertise, diligent attention to detail, and smart feedback have been invaluable in ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and validity of our measurement tool. Their dedication to advancing research in our field has played a crucial role in strengthening the foundation of our study. We are sincerely thankful for their contributions, which have significantly enhanced the quality and credibility of our research endeavor.

They also like to extend their thanks of appreciation to their family, peers, friends, and classmates, including both junior, and senior fellow nursing students for their cooperative efforts, insightful suggestions, cheers of motivation, and memorable moments shared during the duration of this research.

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